

Figure S1. Principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) of bacterial communities in plant-based meat alternatives (PBMA) stored at 4°C. **A.** Jaccard PCoA results for pea-based meats (PBMs) and soy-based meats (SBMs) on Day 0 (sell-by date) and Day 7 (seven days after the sell-by date). **B.** Bray-Curtis PCoA results for PBMs and SBMs on Day 0 and Day 7. **C.** Weighted Unifrac PCoA results for PBMs and SBMs on Day 0 and Day 7. Pairwise comparisons were conducted using pairwise PERMANOVA.

Figure S2. Principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) of fungal communities in plant-based meat alternatives (PBMs) stored at 4°C. **A.** Jaccard PCoA results for pea-based meats (PBMs) and soy-based meats (SBMs) on Day 0 (sell-by date) and Day 7 (seven days after the sell-by date). **B.** Bray-Curtis PCoA results for PBMs and SBMs on Day 0 and Day 7. **C.** Weighted Unifrac PCoA results for PBMs and SBMs on Day 0 and Day 7. Pairwise comparisons were conducted using pairwise PERMANOVA.

Figure S3. Indigenous microbial community composition of PBM (Pea-Based-Meat) and SBM (Soy-Based-Meat). Bacterial taxonomic classification at the phylum level. Percentages are only shown for relative abundances of 3% or more. **P:** Pea. **S:** Soy. **Gr:** Ground. **Br:** Burger. **N:** New size. **Lt:** Lite. **0:** Sell-by date. **7:** Seven days after the sell-by date.

Figure S4. Indigenous microbial community composition of PBM (Pea-Based-Meat) and SBM (Soy-Based-Meat). Fungal taxonomic classification at the phylum level. Percentages are only shown for relative abundances of 3% or more. **P:** Pea. **S:** Soy. **Gr:** Ground. **Br:** Burger. **N:** New size. **Lt:** Lite. **0:** Sell-by date. **7:** Seven days after the sell-by date.